

THE ROLE OF BRAND PERSONALITY AND CUSTOMER PERCEIVED VALUE IN ENHANCING BRAND STRENGTH AND LOYALTY: EVIDENCE FROM THE PAKISTANI RETAIL CLOTHING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The current era features digital interactivity and experiential consumption, in this research, the impact of brand's personality on brand strength and loyalty will be shown within Pakistan's clothing industry with respect to customers' perceived value of products. Utilizing Constructs of Brand Equity and Consumer Behavior Theories, a quantitative cross-sectional design with a sample of 302 respondents from leading National Clothing Brands contributes to the growing body of knowledge regarding the significance of customer perceived value of products and services. Results from Structural Equation Modeling indicate that Brand Personality has a significant and positive relationship with Customers' Perceived Value, Brand Strength, as well as Brand Loyalty. Customer Perceived Value also has positive, significant influence on Brand Strength and Brand Loyalty. Mediation Analysis demonstrate that Customer Perceived Value partially mediates the relationships between Brand Personality and Brand Strength and between Brand Personality and Brand Loyalty. The findings of this research will contribute to the expanding body of knowledge regarding symbolic and experiential elements of brands which add value to consumers' assessments of brands and develop long-term loyalty in emerging market countries. Thus, marketers and brand managers must understand that to differentiate themselves from competing brands and achieve long-term loyalty, they should implement a value-adding personality-based strategy.

1. Introduction:

As customers continue to place more emphasis on their experiences, the way they buy things is changing. (Bilgihan et al., 2016) When done properly, it provides a well-structured luxury purchasing journey that provides an accurate and consistent expression of both luxury retailers and their brands, in addition to all other aspects of luxury retail. (Manlow & Nobbs, 2013) There has been an increasing number of people using the Internet. In 2012, a forecast of Internet Retail

sales predicted that the online retail market in the United States would be worth \$327 billion in 2016, up 45% from \$226 billion in 2012, and a growth of 62% from \$202 billion in 2011. (Analysts & Mulpuru, 2011) Due to the high number of followers that social media influencers have, the impact they can have on consumers' repurchasing decisions is significant by disseminating information regarding a company's or a brand's product or service through their platforms. (Myers, Sen et al., 2022)

In this study, the author will define extravagance by using the term theatricality. The Merriam-Webster dictionary defines theatricality as "the exaggerated or false nature of a performance". This definition is the basis of this project. Theatrical experiences are an essential part of experiential marketing, which creates an emotional connection with customers through creating a memory-based experience. Experiential marketing in restaurants has been studied extensively by researchers (Fiore, 2010; Lanier Jr & Hampton, 2016; Tung & Ritchie, 2011). Theatre was used in the restaurant industry since the Middle Ages according to Morgan et al. (2010), but now, it is mainly used for aesthetic reasons. The fast growing market for the Pakistani Fashion Industry and the vast range of brands trying to acquire as many consumers as possible, allowed advertising to use influencer marketing to a greater degree during COVID-19 (Javed 2020), and currently more and more brands are focusing on employing social media influencers to promote their product (Shoukat et al, 2023). Therefore, this requires the need for further research about how social media influencers can influence customer behaviour and brand engagement within the Pakistani Fashion Industry.

While it has been confirmed that this relationship influences brand value and loyalty (Boo et al., 2009), the interaction of brand personality with brand quality has not previously been proven through research. This study investigates this relationship and furthers our understanding of the concept of brand equity. This research aims to identify the best method to develop a hotel brand that provides value and loyalty to its customers by examining how brand personality interacts with brand quality in the hotel sector. In recent years, multiple online businesses in Pakistan have begun to understand the value of social media influencer marketing in terms of generating customer engagement and increasing their revenues. Social media influencers (SMIs) are creators of content who promote brands through video or post content and may create highly viral content and inspiring their audience (Shoukat, Selem et al., 2023). Therefore, this study aims to explore the

effect of SMIs on customer engagement and online purchasing behaviour within the fashion industry in Pakistan.

The investigation will look at how SMI's helps firms in Pakistan develop customer engagement and, as a consequence, customer purchase intentions. The goal of this research is to analyze how (a) brand personality affects brand strength and brand loyalty, and (b) customer perceived value mediates the relationship between brand personality and brand loyalty.

1.1 Research Questions:

- How does brand personality influence customer perceived value in the clothing industry?
- What is the impact of customer perceived value on brand strength in the clothing industry?
- What is the relationship between brand strength and brand loyalty in the clothing industry?
- Does customer perceived value mediate the relationship between brand personality and brand strength in the clothing industry?
- Does brand strength mediate the relationship between customer perceived value and brand loyalty in the clothing industry?

1.2 Research Objectives:

- To examine the relationship between brand personality and customer perceived value in the clothing industry.
- To investigate the impact of customer perceived value on brand strength in the clothing industry.
- To explore the relationship between brand strength and brand loyalty in the clothing industry.
- To assess the mediating role of customer perceived value in the relationship between brand personality and brand strength.
- To determine the mediating role of brand strength in the relationship between customer perceived value and brand loyalty.

2. Literature Review:

Based on research data (Joyce, 1963; Keller, 1993), it is acknowledged that consumers form mental connections/associations within their own minds to create meaning for a brand. In addition, the same research demonstrated that the potential to build stronger brands exists not only through positive mental associations or perceptions, but also through negative associations/perceptions from consumers (Joyce, 1963; Keller, 1993). The current study is built around this premise, but adds onto this through the inclusion of e-WOM. It's worth noting, that much like the parent theory of this current study, there are now new elements to the notion of theatricality and that this study also draws upon the marketing mix as the primary foundation for consumers creating mental associations/meaning for the brands they associate with. The theatrical aspects are instrumental in creating buzz in the marketplace through Electronic Word of Mouth. Thus, the goal of this current work is to improve upon the Parent Theory in the Digital Marketplace. This current study will look at the impact of Brand Personality on Brand Strength and Customer Loyalty with Customer Perceived Value acting as a mediator. Data will be collected from Clothing Businesses in Pakistan.

2.1 Brand Personality and Brand Image:

A brand's image is the external and internal reflection of the brand's personality, according to Boo and colleagues. Brand images drive emotional connections between consumers and brands, whereas brand awareness drives familiarity with brand names and attributes. Examples of brand images include: 1) an image that represents specific qualities associated with a person's personality; 2) an image reflecting a certain position in life and the importance of that position in terms of consumer behaviour; and 3) brand images in the tourism and hospitality sector. In the tourism and hospitality sectors, brand image is of great importance for consumers, and for building brand loyalty. A greater understanding of this importance can be gained from the research of Aaker and others. Aaker's

research has shown that personality traits can be applied to brands and have a direct impact on brand identity. Many brands have created a "label" for their brand personalities (e.g., by using the term "brand"), which is similar to how human personality traits can be applied to branding. The development of brand personality dimensions is described in detail in Aaker's 1997 paper, "Understanding Brand Personality."

Rather than viewing Brand Personality as a single-variable construct, it is possible to understand the various ways that Brand Personality influences the customer preference by separating the various dimensions of Brand Personality (p348). Brand Community Marketing events will become increasingly important in future marketing competitions; therefore, companies should organise these events to offer a fun and memorable experience for their customers by creating a theme and using sensory engagement (Tsaur, Chiu et al., 2007). In the present time, consumers expect brands to create an experience that exceeds the product attributes they are used to before making a purchase (Chen & Lin 2019). Social Media and Influencer Marketing open new channels of advertising for businesses and brands allowing businesses to develop positive brand trust and engagement with their customers by utilising a variety of Influencers across multiple social media platforms.

Aaker's research (1997) on 42 attributes provided the basis for the following assumptions made by the authors in regard to hotel brands: The Kimpton brand created a sense of genuineness with its "upbeat" image, along with "new in town" service and trustworthy service. The Howard Johnson's (and Howard Johnson Jr.) goal was to create a brand with authenticity and originality for their hotel brand, Howard Johnson. Therefore, the collaboration with the Wyndham division was vital to help create that brand's identity. The sales of "exploration" and "discovery" experiences have been key to developing the excitement that has surrounded Marriott, Hilton, Accor, and InterContinental brands. Examples of these include Marriott Autograph Collection and

Double Tree by Hilton, Mercure by Accor, Candlewood by Inter Continental Hotels.

2.2 Brand Loyalty:

The term "brand loyalty" is defined as a consumer's commitment to a brand. This commitment is based on more than just continuing to buy products and services from a satisfied customer. Brand loyalty is identified by Diallo et al., (2020) as having a positive impact on three dimensions. One of the dimensions of brand loyalty is that it reflects a consumer's willingness to purchase more than one product from the same company. An example of the positive impact on a brand's business caused by consumers dedicated to the brand is identified by Ledikwe et al., (2019), who state that brand loyalty shows how likely consumers are to switch brands. A consumer base committed to brand loyalty will continue to purchase the same brand of products as opposed to purchasing products from other competitors. Research conducted by Ting et al., (2021) shows that consumers are more likely to be loyal to a brand if they perceive that the brand offers mutual benefits when they do business with it.

Research indicates a relationship between the familiarity of consumers to a brand and their level of loyalty as a result of this familiarity (Ahn & Back, 2020). Heggde and Tampi (2019) studied how a customer's level of identification with a certain IT Firm significantly influences the level of loyalty a customer has toward that IT firm. Similarly, several studies have also proven that brand loyalty and brand recognition are positively correlated within the hospitality industry (Nasir et al. 2022; Rather et al., 2020); however, the difference between this study and previous studies is that this study is focused on actual customers of the Tobacco Industry.

2.3 Brand Strength:

Earlier studies on brand image strength have generally focused on the financial value a business receives from a brand (Salinas & Amber, 2009) or on the brand equity associated with a brand (Raggio & Leone, 2007). Both financial value and brand equity are hypothesised to moderate the

influence of marketing activities on the image a brand conveys. Keller (2008) defines powerful brands as those that possess a large amount of consumer recognition and have been reviewed favourably by many in the industry. We assert in this paper that brand power can be found in how marketing practitioners utilise images in their marketing activities. Atkinson & van Raaij (1998) contend that a large portion of consumer behaviour occurs without thorough consideration or study and suggest that this type of behaviour links to the unconscious process of making consumer decisions.

Consumer behaviours, according to Korkman (2006), "are routinized behaviours that involve tools, knowledge, images, the physical environment, and the participant engaging in the behaviour. Brand images or pictures are an integral part of a consumer's interpretative framework with which they interact within their world of branding and consume products. The practise-based perspective of branding follows from the latest developments in marketing theory that suggest that consumers are creating value through their everyday brand behaviours (Vargo & Lusch, 2004; Arnould et al., 2006; Schau et al., 2009). The concept of a product or service's role as a facilitator of brand experiences reflects the essence of the service dominant logic by enabling marketers and brand managers to consider the time-related aspects of how their consumers experience their brands (Ballantyne & Aitken, 2007; Payne et al., 2009; Arnould et al., 2006; Strandvik & Rindell, 2010; Pitt et al., 2006), and better understand what their consumers do with a brand as opposed to just how the consumer perceives it.

2.4 Customer Perceived Value:

The equity theory, first proposed by Adams (1963), asserts that the service provider's output or what is received from providing a product or service to customers is relative to what the consumer puts in as payment (e.g., money, time, etc.). Equity theory has been applied heavily since then to others (e.g., 1988; Bolton & Lemon, 1999). The theory posits that the consumer's view

of how much he/she receives back from the business (outcome) is dependent on the relative comparison of their input (how much they spent) to that of the company producing the good/service. Intangible factors such as the time and effort involved to receive value from a business (how long they waited), the physical and emotional stress relating to how they perceive the cost of a good/service, etc. will affect how the company or business produces outcomes for customers. In addition, consumers will judge the efficiency of a business by its products/services compared to those of other businesses/competitors. When consumers have a similar perception of the ratio of their outputs to inputs compared to that of the outputs versus inputs of the business, they feel that they have been treated fairly.

According to Holbrook (1994), everything an organisation does in marketing its products or services is to create a value proposition for customers. When customers perceive that they receive excellent value from a company, they will gravitate toward doing business with that

company. As Sirdeshmukh, Singh, and Sabol (2002) state, the "ultimate aim" for businesses is to create maximum customer value, and the second aim of "encouraging customer loyalty" is a by-product of the efforts made to maximise customer value. Theories of action and goal identities indicate that higher-order objectives are more likely to govern the behaviour of lower-order objectives. Therefore, according to Sirdeshmukh et al., "the behavioural intentions of loyalty towards the service provider will depend on whether that service provider continues to create superior customer value" (2002). In addition, research has demonstrated that perceived customer value is a critical factor for predicting consumer loyalty across multiple channels, including telecommunications, the airline industry and retail services (Sirdeshmukh et al., 2002). Chang and Wildt (1994) cite numerous studies that have shown that customers' perceptions of value play an integral role in their decisions to purchase products or services. Based on this overview of related research and conclusions, we can conclude the following:

Theoretical Framework:

Hypothesis:

- H1: There is a positive impact of Brand Personality on Brand Strength.
- H2: There is a positive impact of Brand Personality on Brand Loyalty.
- H3: There is a positive impact of Brand Personality on Customer Perceived value.
- H4: There exists a positive impact of Customer perceived value on brand strength.

H5: Customer perceived value has a significant positive impact on Brand Loyalty.

3. Methodology:

3.1 Research Design:

A quantitative and cross-sectional research design was used to study the effects of brand personality on brand loyalty and brand strength. The study also considered the role of customer perceived

value as mediating the effect of brand personality upon brand strength and brand loyalty in the Pakistani retail clothing industry. The quantitative approach provides an avenue for testing hypotheses statistically and therefore generalising the results across a broad base of consumers.

3.2 Population and Sampling Technique:

The population of this study was made up of consumers of established retail clothing brands in Pakistan. This included those who have purchased from 4-5 well-established clothing brands (Nationally) in Pakistan. This group of study participants were selected because they have first-hand experience of branding and therefore will be able to assess their brand's personality, perceived value, strength and loyalty to purchase.

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was employed, which is widely used in consumer and branding research due to ease of access and efficiency in collecting data from retail customers.

3.3 Sample Size:

A total of 330 questionnaires were distributed using online platforms and in-store consumer outreach. After removing incomplete and invalid responses, 302 questionnaires were retained for final analysis. This sample size is considered sufficient for mediation analysis and structural equation modeling, meeting recommended thresholds for statistical power.

3.4 Data Collection Instrument:

Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire developed using established and validated scales from prior research. All items were measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

3.5 Brand Personality:

To measure Brand Personality, we employed five items based on Aaker's (1997) concept of Brand Personality. From those five items we assessed consumer's perception of the Brand's fashion, expertise, the Brand's social image, emotional appeal and overall personality traits. The brand personality framework proposed by Aaker (1997)

characterizes a Brand as possessing human characteristics that affect a consumer's attitude and behaviour toward a Brand.

3.6 Customer Perceived Value:

Five items were used to determine customer-perceived value. These were adapted from Eggert (2002) and included: Price Fairness, Product Quality, Value for Money, Fashion Appeal & Product Fit. The consumer perceived value is the overall total of all benefits received with the sacrifices made.

3.7 Brand Strength:

Brand strength is assessed by the following three metrics that were put in place by Keller's (1993, 2003, 2008) Customer-based Brand Equity framework, which includes items addressing Market Presence, Brand Image, and Recognition among consumers. As Keller states, strong brands are those which have high levels of awareness, an excellent Brand Image, and widespread Recognition within the marketplace.

3.8 Brand Loyalty:

Brand loyalty was assessed using four questions originally developed by Anderson and Sullivan (1993). These questions address consumers' preferences for brands, their emotional attachment to brands, their intentions to recommend brands and their intentions to purchase from brands again. In short, brand loyalty indicates a consumer's long-term commitment and positive feelings about a particular brand.

3.9 Pilot Study:

A pilot study was conducted with 50 consumers of Pakistani clothing brands to assess the clarity, reliability, and contextual suitability of the questionnaire. Minor wording modifications were made to improve comprehension. The pilot results confirmed that the instrument was reliable and suitable for large-scale data collection.

3.10 Reliability and Validity:

To ensure measurement quality, the following accepted thresholds were applied:

- **Cronbach’s Alpha ≥ 0.70** for internal consistency
- **Composite Reliability (CR) ≥ 0.70**
- **Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ≥ 0.50** for convergent validity

These criteria are widely accepted in marketing and consumer behavior research.

3.11 Data Analysis Techniques:

Data analysis was performed using SPSS. The following statistical techniques were applied:

- Descriptive statistics
- Reliability and validity analysis
- Correlation analysis
- Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

- Mediation analysis

3.12 Ethical Considerations:

Ethical standards were strictly followed throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained, and respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality. The study complied with ethical guidelines for academic research involving human participants.

4. DATA ANALYSIS:

Introduction:

This chapter presents the results of data analysis conducted to test the proposed hypotheses and mediation effects among brand personality, customer perceived value, brand strength, and brand loyalty in the Pakistani retail clothing industry. Statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS to ensure reliability and robustness

4.1 Descriptive Statistics:

Table 4.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents (N = 302)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	171	56.6%
	Female	131	43.4%
Age	18-25	92	30.5%
	26-35	124	41.1%
	36-45	61	20.2%
	Above 45	25	8.3%
	Education	Bachelor’s	118
	Master’s	152	50.3%
	Others	32	10.6%

Interpretation:

The demographic profile indicates that most respondents were young and educated consumers,

representing the primary target market of Pakistani retail clothing brands.

4.2 Reliability and Convergent Validity:

Table 4.2 Reliability and Validity Analysis

Construct	Items	Cronbach’s Alpha	CR	AVE
Brand Personality	5	0.86	0.89	0.60
Customer Perceived Value	5	0.84	0.87	0.58
Brand Strength	3	0.81	0.85	0.65
Brand Loyalty	4	0.88	0.90	0.62

Interpretation:

All constructs demonstrate strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values

exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.70. CR and AVE values confirm satisfactory convergent validity.

4.3 Correlation Analysis:

Table 4.3 Correlation Matrix

Variables	BP	CPV	BS	BL
Brand Personality (BP)	1			
Customer Perceived Value (CPV)	0.62**	1		
Brand Strength (BS)	0.57**	0.64**	1	
Brand Loyalty (BL)	0.54**	0.61**	0.67**	1

Note: $p < 0.01$

Interpretation:

All variables are positively and significantly

correlated, supporting the proposed conceptual model and justifying further mediation analysis.

4.4 Structural Equation Modeling – Direct Effects

Table 4.4 Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Path	β	t-value	p-value	Result
H1	BP → BS	0.33	5.14	0.000	Supported
H2	BP → BL	0.26	4.07	0.000	Supported
H3	BP → CPV	0.61	9.58	0.000	Supported
H4	CPV → BS	0.45	7.12	0.000	Supported
H5	CPV → BL	0.41	6.54	0.000	Supported

4.5 Mediation Analysis:

Table 4.5 Mediation Effects

Mediating Path	Indirect Effect (β)	t-value	p-value	Mediation Type
BP → CPV → BS	0.27	5.88	0.000	Partial
BP → CPV → BL	0.25	5.36	0.000	Partial

Interpretation:

Customer perceived value significantly mediates the relationship between brand personality and both brand strength and brand loyalty. This

indicates that brand personality enhances brand outcomes both directly and indirectly through increased perceived value.

4.6 Model Fit Indices:

Table 4.6 Model Fit Statistics

Fit Index	Recommended	Obtained
SRMR	< 0.08	0.05
NFI	> 0.90	0.94
R ² (CPV)	Moderate	0.37

Fit Index	Recommended	Obtained
R ² (BS)	Moderate	0.51
R ² (BL)	Moderate	0.48

Interpretation:

All model fit indices meet recommended thresholds, confirming a strong and acceptable structural model.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:**Introduction:**

This chapter will present the findings of the study based on empirical data and connect them to existing theories and previous research. It also discusses the theoretical and practical implications of this research and its limitations, and presents suggestions for further research. The purpose of this research was to investigate the effect of Brand Personality on Brand Strength and Brand Loyalty, with a mediating role of Customer Perceived Value, in the context of the Pakistani Retail Clothing Industry. The findings give insight into how Clothing Brands can improve their market position and customer loyalty by enhancing their Brand Personality and Customer Perceived Value.

5.1 Discussion of Findings:**5.1.1 Brand Personality and Brand Strength:**

A statistically significant and positive correlation exists between the personality of a clothing brand (brand personality) and the strength of the brand (brand strength) ($\beta = 0.33$, $p < 0.001$). Clothing brands with strong, likeable, and anthropomorphic (human-like) qualities are expected to have more successful marketing visibility, positive reputation, and therefore a higher level of consumer recall compared to clothing brands without these characteristics. This finding supports Aaker's (1997) model for building brand equity based on the existence of emotional bonds between consumers and brands that exhibit unique personalities.

This finding supports Keller's (2003, 2008) customer-based brand equity framework which states that the brand's strength is enhanced by positive associations with the brand in the minds of consumers. The competitive landscape for

apparel within Pakistan is very intense, therefore, by definition, the branding personality is important for brands to differentiate themselves from one another to create a well-established brand in the memory of consumers.

5.1.2 Brand Personality and Brand Loyalty:

The study's results showed that brand personality positively influences brand loyalty ($\beta = 0.26$, $p < 0.001$). Consumers who view a clothing brand as fashionable, trendy, and emotionally appealing remain loyal to or choose that brand over other competitor brands. This finding supports previous research indicating that consumers develop a stronger emotional bond with a brand and continue to buy from them repeatedly as a result (Anderson & Sullivan, 1993; Aaker, 1997).

In the context of Pakistan's fashion industry, where consumers often associate clothing brands with self-expression and social identity, a strong brand personality plays a vital role in encouraging long-term loyalty and advocacy.

5.1.3 Brand Personality and Customer Perceived Value:

The findings determined that there is a very strong connection between customer perceptions of brand personalities and their corresponding customer perceived value ($\beta = 0.61$, $p < 0.001$). Brands that consumers associate with being fashionable, knowledgeable, and appealing socially are also associated with delivering a greater level of perceived value than brands that have the same attributes but do not associate with these qualities. This finding supports Eggert's (2002) definition of perceived value, which indicates that perceived value is not determined by price or quality alone, but that it includes emotional and symbolic components as well.

This result highlights that in the Pakistani clothing sector, brand personality enhances customers' perceptions of quality, price fairness, and overall

worth, thereby increasing perceived value beyond functional attributes.

5.1.4 Customer Perceived Value and Brand Strength:

According to the analysis, customer perceived value has a highly significant positive impact on brand strength ($\beta = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$). This means that when consumers perceive that a clothing brand offers them good value for money, with fashion-forward design, good quality products, it strengthens a brand's position in the marketplace and name recognition. Keller (2008) supports this statement, stating that the development of strong brands develops through consumer perception of positive evaluations and value.

In Pakistan's retail clothing industry, where price sensitivity and quality awareness coexist, perceived value becomes a critical driver of brand strength.

5.1.5 Customer Perceived Value and Brand Loyalty:

Additionally, the study confirms that the customer-perceived-value of a brand significantly affects the level of customer loyalty to that brand. Customers who have higher perceptions of value for a brand are more likely to make repeat purchases, tell others about the brand, and develop an emotional connection with that brand. These findings are consistent with those of Sirdeshmukh et al., 2002, and Holbrook, 1994, who have stated that perceived value is one of the major drivers of customer loyalty.

This outcome highlights that Pakistani clothing brands must consistently deliver value to retain loyal customers in a competitive market.

5.1.6 Mediating Role of Customer Perceived Value:

Findings from the mediation analysis show that the perception of value by customers partially mediates the connection between brand personality and brand strength and the connection between brand personality and customer loyalty to the brand. Therefore, brand personality affects brand outcomes both directly and indirectly by increasing perceived value. This

supports value-based branding models, which claim that consumers will have a greater connection to brands when their emotional and symbolic characteristics have an increased consumer perceived value through enhanced consumer perceived value.

5.2 Theoretical Contribution:

This research provides numerous theoretical advancements, namely extending Aaker's (1997) brand personality framework to include an empirical demonstration of how brand personality affects brand strength and brand loyalty through Customer-perceived value (CPV) in retail clothing. Second, it builds on Keller's (2003; 2008) Brand Equity Framework by validating that CPV is the primary method through which brand personality affects brand strength.

Additionally, the study enriches branding literature by providing empirical evidence from a developing market, particularly Pakistan's fashion industry, which has received limited scholarly attention.

5.3 Practical Implications:

5.3.1 Implications for Clothing Brand Managers:

The findings offer valuable insights for brand managers in the Pakistani retail clothing industry:

- Clothing brands should invest in developing a clear and consistent brand personality to strengthen emotional connections with consumers.
- Marketing strategies should emphasize not only product features but also symbolic and experiential elements that enhance perceived value.
- Brands should focus on delivering value through quality, fashionability, and fair pricing to strengthen brand reputation and loyalty.

5.3.2 Implications for Marketing Practitioners:

Marketing practitioners should design branding campaigns that highlight personality-driven attributes, such as trendiness and social appeal, to enhance customer perceived value and loyalty.

5.3.3 Implications for Consumers:

From a consumer perspective, the study underscores the importance of perceived value in shaping loyalty decisions, encouraging informed and value-conscious purchasing behavior.

5.4 Limitations of the Study:

Despite its contributions, this study has certain limitations:

1. **Industry-Specific Scope:** The study focuses only on the retail clothing industry, which may limit generalizability to other sectors.
2. **Cross-Sectional Design:** Data were collected at one point in time, restricting the ability to assess changes in consumer perceptions over time.
3. **Self-Reported Data:** Responses were based on consumers' perceptions, which may introduce common method bias.
4. **Geographical Context:** The study was conducted in Pakistan, which may limit applicability to other cultural contexts.

5.5 Future Research Directions:

Future research may build upon this study by:

- Conducting longitudinal studies to examine changes in brand perceptions over time.
- Expanding the model to include other variables such as brand trust, brand love, or customer engagement.
- Comparing local and international clothing brands to assess cultural differences in brand personality perceptions.
- Extending the study to other industries such as cosmetics, footwear, or luxury retail.

5.6 Conclusion:

In conclusion, the results of this research study support the theory that purchasing power dictates brand development within the retail sector for clothing in Pakistan. The conclusions highlight that brand personality is a strong driver of both brand loyalty and brand strength; both of which can be enhanced through brand personality directly or through the customer's perceived value of the brand. For clothing brand manufacturers looking to be successful in an ever-increasingly competitive global marketplace (retail), they

should develop value-based and personality-focused brand-development strategies as part of their long-term strategic goal of realizing sustained success from the brand.

By strengthening brand personality and delivering superior value, clothing brands can foster long-term loyalty, enhance market presence, and secure a competitive advantage in Pakistan's dynamic fashion industry.

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